

followed by condensation via cyclisation furnished the corresponding 3-benzoylaminothiazolidin-4-ones (4). On the other hand, fusion of compounds 2 with thioglycolic acid at moderate temperature gave the thioethers (5) in good yield (Scheme 1).

- a ; R = H, Ar = C₆H₄.NO₂-4
- b ; R = H, Ar = C₆H₄.N(Me)₂-4
- c ; R = H, Ar = C₆H₄.Cl₂-2,4
- d ; R = H, Ar = C₆H₄.Cl₂-2,6
- e ; R = H, Ar = C₆H₄(OMe)OH-3,4
- f ; R = H, Ar = Pyridin-2-yl
- g ; R = H, Ar = Furan-2-yl
- h ; R = CH₃, Ar = Pyridin-4-yl
- i ; R = CH₃, Ar = Indol-3-yl
- j ; R = CH₃, Ar = C₆H₄.OH-2
- k ; R = Anthraquinon-1-yl
- l ; R = Indol-2-one-3-yl

Scheme 1

Biologically Active Thiazolidinone. Part-III. Synthesis and Fungal Toxicities of Substituted Thiazolidinone, Thioether and N-Benzoyl Heterocyclic Compounds from Benzoyl Acid Hydrazones

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IN view of the considerable biological importance of thiazolidinone derivatives^{1,2}, substituted thiazolidin-4-ones, thioether and N-benzoyl heterocyclic compounds of probable pharmacological effects have been prepared.

It is reported that benzoic acid hydrazide (1) condensed with aromatic aldehydes³ in ethanolic acid gives the corresponding hydrazones (2a-l). These hydrazones (2a-c, e, h, i, l) are now fused with 4-chlorothiophenol to give the respective thioethers (3a-g). The structure of 3 was deduced from elemental analyses and spectral studies. Its spectra of 3 showed disappearance of C=N band with the appearance of bands at 3 570-3 300 (OH, NH-NH, acid hydrazide) and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C new thioether band).

The main aim of the present work was to synthesise the substituted thiazolidinones and to study their fungitoxicities. Thus, addition of thioglycolic acid to the appropriate hydrazones in dry benzene²

The structures of the thiazolidinones (4) and thioethers (5) were established on the basis of their ir, uv and pmr spectral data. The structural difference between compounds 4 and 5 lies in the presence of two signals at δ 6.8 and 10.1 ppm due to NH-C(SMe) and NH-COPh in compounds 5, for one NH at δ 10.2 ppm in compounds 4.

Acylation of compounds 2a, c, d, j using benzoyl chloride in DMF afforded N¹-dibenzoyl-N²-arylidene hydrazones (6a-d) which underwent condensation with hydrazine hydrate in sodium ethoxide to give 3,5-diphenyl-4-azomethanehydrazones-1,2,4-triazoles (7a, b), while the condensation with guanidine hydrochloride⁴ under the same conditions led to the formation of 2-imino-4,6-diphenyl-5-azomethanehydrazones-1,3,5-triazine (8). On the other hand, N¹-benzoyl-3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles (9) were synthesised from the reaction of compound 1 with benzoylacetone in glacial acetic acid and fused sodium acetate⁵, while refluxing the same with 2-benzoylbenzoic acid under the same conditions gave N²-benzoyl-4-phenylphthalazinone (10) (Scheme 2). Structures of the compounds were supported by their elemental analyses and ir, uv and pmr spectral data.

Antifungal activity: The *in vitro* antifungal activity of the compounds was tested by inhibition of mycelial growth of *Penicillium italicum* at different concentrations by disc method⁴ using DMF as a solvent. The growth was determined by measuring

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colony diameter (mm) and growth inhibition calculated with reference to the control⁶. ED₅₀ values were determined by regression analysis of the log-probit transformed data⁷.

The results show that **3f**, **5a** and **6b** are more fungitoxic than others (100% inhibition at concentrations 5, 20 and 20 μg dm⁻³), while the ED₅₀ value of **2a** produced 50% inhibition of the fungal growth at concentration 4.5 μg dm⁻³. The results also show that compound **4d** at 1.7 μg dm⁻³ produced the same effect. This indicates that **4d** is more toxic than the former.

Regarding the structure-activity relationships, it is clear that the activity of compound **2a** is increased by substituting benzoyl group with hydrogen atom (**6b**). It is well-known that compounds containing sulphur atom are fungitoxic and used to control plant diseases. Thus, compounds **3f** and **5a** are more fungitoxic than the others and aryl group attached to sulphur atom increases the activity of

the compound rather than methyl group, which agrees with the findings of Von Schmeling⁸.

Experimental

M.ps. reported are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by paper-chromatogram (chloroform-ethyl acetate). Uv spectra (ethanol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR 4 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on an EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Condensation of benzoic acid hydrazide (1) with aldehydes and ketones. Formation of 2a-1: To a solution of **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 25 ml) were added the appropriate aldehyde or ketone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 25 ml) and drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h, left overnight and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{max} **2j** 3 500 (OH), 3 200 (NH), 3 020 (CH aromatic), 2 990 (CH aliph.), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 580 (C=N), 1 480 (def. CH₂) and 1 000 cm⁻¹ (*o*-substituted phenyl); λ_{max} 320, 275 and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	247 ^a	80
2b	182 ^a	60
2c	220 ^a	70
2d	230 ^a	90
2e	174 ^a	70
2f	211 ^a	60
2g	190 ^a	70
2h	185 ^a	80
2i	241 ^a	90
2l	195 ^a	60
2k	300 ^a	60
2l	284 ^a	70
3a	83 ^b	50
3b	110 ^c	60
3c	67 ^b	60
3d	85 ^b	65
3e	80 ^a	60
3f	165 ^a	70
3g	150 ^e	60
4a	165 ^f	70
4b	215 ^c	80
4c	255 ^f	65
4d	190 ^g	65
5a	110 ^a	80
5b	193 ^a	90
6a	165 ^g	70
6b	190 ^g	75
6c	117 ^a	75
6d	185 ^a	80
7a	120 ^h	90
7b	187 ^a	80
8	244 ^a	70
9	205 ⁱ	90
10	95 ⁱ	90

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S and Cl analysis.

**Crystallised from: ^aEtOH, ^bbenzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), ^cbenzene, ^dethylbenzene, ^etoluene, ^fdioxane, ^gMeOH, ^hDMF, ⁱAcOH.

195 nm; δ 2a 3.3 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.4–8.0, 8.2–8.5 (4H, m, SH, C₆H₄NO₂ and C₆H₅CO) and 12.0 (1H, s, NH).

Addition of 4-chlorothiophenol to hydrazones 2.
Formation of 3a–g: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and 4-chlorothiophenol (0.02 mol) was heated at 180° (oil-bath) for 6 h. The solid obtained after trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) was recrystallised from benzene to give arylmercaptobenzoic acid hydrazides 3 (Table 1); ν_{\max} 3b 3 570–3 300br (OH–NH–NH), 3 020 (CH arom.), 2 900–2 820 (CH aliph.), 1 620 (C=O hydrazide), 1 490 (def. CH₂), 1 090 (S–R) and 1 000 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted phenyl); λ_{\max} 245 and 200 nm.

Reaction of mercaptoacetic acid with 2.
Formation of 4a–d: Mercaptoacetic acid (0.25 mol) was added to a well-stirred solution of 2 (0.05 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 8–10 h, then excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. On cooling, the resulting solid mass was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 80–100°) (Table 1); ν_{\max} 4b 3 200 (NH), 3 020 (CH arom.), 2 980–2 800 (CH aliph.), 1 660 (C=O ketone), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 480 (def. CH₂) and 1 020 cm⁻¹ (*p*-substituted phenyl); λ_{\max} 290 and 195 nm; δ 4b 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂ of thiazolidinone), 3.6 (s, CH=of pyridyl-2), 7.3–7.7 (4H, m, pyridine), 7.8–8.0 (5H, m, Ph) and 10.2 (1H, s, NHCOPh).

Fusion of 2 with mercaptoacetic acid.
Formation of 5a, b: A mixture of 2d, i (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.2 mol) was refluxed at 200° (oil-bath) for 6 h. The resulting solid was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to give methylmercaptobenzoic acid hydrazide 5 (Table 1); ν_{\max} 5b 3 300–3 100br (OH–NH), 3 010 (CH arom.), 2 900 (CH aliph.), 1 680 (C=O amide), 1 480 (def. CH₂) and 1 170 cm⁻¹ (S–R); λ_{\max} 285, 230 and 205 nm; δ 5a 3.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (1H, s, =CHAr), 6.8 (1H, s, OH), 7.2–7.9 (m, phenyl and aryl protons) and 10.1 (1H, s, NH).

Benzoylation of 2.
Formation of 6a–d: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in the presence of DMF (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled, poured into cold water and filtered. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{\max} 6b 3 740 (OH), 3 040 (CH arom.), 2 990 (CH aliph.), 1 730 (C=O ketone), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 590 (C=N), 1 480 (def. CH₂), and 1 080 cm⁻¹ (*o*-substituted phenyl); λ_{\max} 300, 220 and 195 nm; δ 6a 3.3 (1H, s, CH=N) and 7–8 (m, diphenyl and aryl protons).

Reaction of N²-dibenzoylhydrazone (6) with hydrazine hydrate.
Formation of 7a, b: Hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.15 mol) was added to a solution of 6 (0.1 mol) in sodium ethoxide (0.23 g Na in 50 ml ethanol) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled and diluted with water. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{\max} 7b 3 390 (OH),

3 020 (CH arom.), 2 900–2 820 (CH aliph.), 1 620 (C=N cyclic), 1 590 (C=N acyclic), 1 480 (def. CH₂) and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (*o*-substituted phenyl); λ_{\max} 305, 260 and 210 nm.

Reaction of 6 with guanidine hydrochloride.
Formation of 8: A suspension of guanidine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in water (10 ml) and 6 (0.01 mol) in sodium ethoxide (0.23 g Na in 25 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The solid obtained was recrystallised (Table 1); ν_{\max} 8 3 200br (NH), 3 020 (CH arom.), 2 910–2 820 (CH aliph.), 1 620 (C=N cyclic), 1 580 (C=N acyclic), 1 480 (def. CH₂) and 1 030 cm⁻¹ (*p*-substituted phenyl); λ_{\max} 220 and 190 nm.

Cyclocondensation of benzoic acid hydrazide (1) with benzoylacetone.
Formation of N¹-(benzoyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazol (9): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and benzoylacetone (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and poured onto ice and the solid obtained was recrystallised (Table 1); δ 9 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.4 (3H, s, pyrazolyl), 7.3–7.7 (5H, m, phenyl) and 7.8–8.0 (5H, m, phenyl CO).

Reaction of 1 with *o*-benzoic acid.
Formation of 10: A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and *o*-benzoylbenzoic acid (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure, cooled in ice and the resulting solid washed with water and recrystallised (Table 1).

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